

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

To the qualitative properties of cross-diffusion coupled system of reaction diffusion

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1. Introduction

Mathematical models of many processes in nature are nonlinear, and their study requires a special approach. This is another reason why computational experimentation is now becoming an almost unique tool for conducting theoretical research in solving applied problems. However, before numerically analyzing the solution of a nonlinear problem, it is necessary to determine the qualitative properties of the solutions that are very important for computation, such as global solvability, nonsolvability, the blow-up in finite time, and studying the asymptotic properties of the solution.

Consider in the domain $Q = \{(t, x) : t > 0, x \in \mathbb{R}^N\}$ the following Cauchy problem of more general cross-diffusion coupled system

$$L_1(u, v) = -\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div} \left(\nu^{m_1-1} |\nabla u|^k |^{p-2} \nabla u \right) + \nu^{\beta_1} = 0$$

$$L_2(u, v) = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div} \left(u^{m_2-1} |\nabla v|^k |^{p-2} \nabla v \right) + u^{\beta_2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$u(0, x) = u_0(x) \geq 0, \quad \nu(0, x) = \nu_0(x) \geq 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^N \quad (2)$$

where $\beta_1, \beta_2, p, m_i > 0$, $i = 1, 2$ are the given numerical parameters characterizing the nonlinear medium, $\nabla(\cdot) = \operatorname{grad}(\cdot)$, $0 \leq u_0(x), \nu_0(x) \in C(\mathbb{R}^N)$ are given functions.

The system (1) serves as a basis for modeling many physical processes [1-7], for example, this system describes the processes of reaction-diffusion, heat conduction, polytrophic filtration of gas and liquid ($p = 2$) in the nonlinear media with source of which is equal to u^{β_i} , $i = 1, 2$. This system are widely used in economics, especially in advanced theoretical, financial, and computational economics. They are essential whenever economic variables change over time and across states (space, capital, risk, wealth).

In the domain where $u = 0$ or $\nabla u = 0$ system (1) degenerates to the system of first order. Therefore, we need to consider weak solution, as classical solutions to (1) may not exist due to degeneracy. Here the problem investigated based on self-similar and approximate self-similar approach [1-5]. It helps to identify properties of solutions such as finite speed of perturbation, blow up in finite time, localization and so on. Moreover, we use method of nonlinear splitting [4] algorithm which allowed constructing the self-similar system.

The system (1) in the case $u(t, x), \nu(t, x) = 0$ becomes degenerate parabolic system. The solution of the system (1) have property *finite speed of a propagation* (FSP) i.e. if

there are the functions $l_1(t)$, $l_2(t)$, when $|x| \geq l_1(t)$ and $|x| \geq l_2(t)$ that $u(t, x) \equiv 0$ and $\nu(t, x) \equiv 0$. In the case $l_1(t), l_2(t) < \infty$ for $\forall t > 0$ solution of the problem (1) is called a *space localization of a perturbation* (SLP). The surfaces $|x| = l_1(t)$ and $|x| = l_2(t)$ are called a *free boundary* or a *front*.

From the physical point of view, it is reasonable to consider weak solution that has properties of the bounded, continuity, and satisfying to the conditions

$$0 \leq u(t, x), \nu(t, x)$$

$$u^{m_1-1} |\nabla u|^{k(p-2)} \nabla u, \nu^{m_2-1} |\nabla \nu|^{k(p-2)} \nabla \nu \in C(\mathbb{Q}),$$

and satisfy to integral identity in distribution sense [3].

In this paper, based on the self-similar analysis of solutions of the system (1) we study the qualitative properties of solutions of the considered system. Asymptotic property of the compactly supported solutions and quenching solution established. Moreover we obtain estimate of solution for fast diffusion, slowly diffusion and for the critical cases. It is proved an existing solution has property a finite speed of propagation (FSP). It is shown that the coefficient of principal term the asymptotic of the solutions satisfied to some system of a nonlinear algebraic equation. Based on, the qualitative properties of the solution numerical analysis of system reaction diffusion carried out.

The Cauchy problem for particular value of numerical parameters of the system (1) and single equation case intensively studied by many authors (see [1-7] and literature therein). Escobedo Herrero [1] considered the following Cauchy problem for semi linear case of system (1)

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \Delta u + \nu^{\beta_1}, \quad \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial t} = \Delta \nu + u^{\beta_2}.$$

They established the following Fujita type critical exponent

$$(\beta_i + 1)/(\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1) = N/2, \quad i = 1, 2$$

and proved that if $\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1 < 0$ then the Cauchy problem has a nonnegative classical and bounded solution $(u(t, x), v(t, x))$ in some strip $S = [0, T) \times \mathbb{R}^N$, $0 < T \leq \infty$. Set $T^* = \sup\{T > 0\}$ remain bounded in S . If $\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1 > 0$ then $T^* = +\infty$, so that solutions can be continued for all positive time. When $\frac{\gamma}{\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1} > \frac{N}{2}$ with $\gamma = \max(\beta_1, \beta_2)$, one has $T^* < +\infty$ for every nontrivial solution (u, v) . T^* is then called the *blow-up time* of the solution. If $\frac{\gamma}{\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1} \leq \frac{N}{2}$, both situations coexist, since some nontrivial solutions remain bounded in any strip S while others exhibit finite blow-up times.

Studying of the different properties of the solutions of the system (1) are complicated problem, even for a particular case of the system (1) [1-5]. In works [1-5] for the system (1) in the case were shown affectivity of the self-similar approach for studying of the different properties of the solutions of the problem (1). Therefore, the method of nonlinear splitting for construction of self-similar equation is given. Below we construct the self-similar system of equations. For this reason we look for the solution $u(t, x), \nu(t, x)$ of system (1) in the

form

$$\begin{cases} u(t, x) = \bar{u}(t) w(\tau(t), x), \\ v(t, x) = \bar{v}(t) z(\tau(t), x), \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where functions

$$\bar{u}(t) = (T + t)^{-\frac{\beta_1 + 1}{\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1}}, \quad \bar{v}(t) = (T + t)^{-\frac{\beta_2 + 1}{\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1}}$$

are solutions of the system of equations

$$\frac{d\bar{u}}{dt} = -\bar{v}^{\beta_1}, \quad \frac{d\bar{v}}{dt} = -\bar{u}^{\beta_2}. \quad (4)$$

The function $\tau(t)$ is chooses as

$$\tau(t) = \int_0^t \bar{u}^{(m_1 + k(p-2))}(\eta) d\eta = \int_0^t \bar{v}^{m_2 + k(p-2)}(\eta) d\eta, \quad \text{if } m_i + k(p-2) - 1 \neq 0, \quad i = 1, 2$$

$$\tau(t) = T + t, \quad \text{if } m_i + k(p-2) - 1 \neq 0, \quad i = 1, 2$$

Transformation (3) leads the equation (1) to the following system

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial \tau} = \nabla \left(w^{m_1 - 1} |\nabla w^k|^{p-2} \nabla w \right) + ((T + t)^{p_1} / p_1) \left(\frac{\beta_1 + 1}{\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1} w + z^{\beta_1} \right)$$

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial \tau} = \nabla \left(z^{m_2 - 1} |\nabla z^k|^{p-2} \nabla z \right) + ((T + t)^{p_2} / p_2) \left(\frac{\beta_2 + 1}{\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1} z + w^{\beta_2} \right)$$

where

$$p_1 = \beta_1 \beta_2 - 1 - (k(p-2) + m_1) (\beta_1 + 1) / (\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1)$$

$$p_2 = \beta_1 \beta_2 - 1 - (k(p-2) + m_2) (\beta_1 + 1) / (\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1).$$

Set $w(\tau, |x|) = f(\xi)$, $z(\tau, |x|) = \psi(\xi)$, where $\xi = |x| / \tau^{1/p}$.

Then for functions $f(\xi)$, $\psi(\xi)$ from (5) we have the following self-similar system of equations

$$\xi^{1-N} \frac{d}{d\xi} \left(\xi^{N-1} f^{m_1-1} \left| \frac{df}{d\xi} \right|^{p-2} \frac{df}{d\xi} \right) + \frac{\xi}{p} \frac{df}{d\xi} + a_1 [(\beta_1 + 1) / (\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1) f + \psi^{\beta_1}] = 0,$$

$$\xi^{1-N} \frac{d}{d\xi} \left(\xi^{N-1} \psi^{m_2-1} \left| \frac{d\psi}{d\xi} \right|^{p-2} \frac{d\psi}{d\xi} \right) + \frac{\xi}{p} \frac{d\psi}{d\xi} + a_2 [(\beta_2 + 1) / (\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1) \psi + f^{\beta_2}] = 0,$$

if $\alpha_1(m_1 + k(p-2)) = \alpha_2(m_2 + k(p-2))$, where $a_i = 1/p_i$, $i = 1, 2$.

1. Fujita type a global solvability and property of a finite speed of a perturbation

Introduce the notations

$$\begin{aligned} u_+(t, x) &= \bar{u}(t) \bar{f}(\xi), & v_+(t, x) &= \bar{v}(t) \bar{\psi}(\xi) \\ \bar{f}(\xi) &= (a - \xi^{p/(p-1)})_+^{q_1}, & \bar{\psi}(\xi) &= (a - \xi^{p/(p-1)})_+^{q_2}, & (n)_+ &= \max(0, n) \\ q &= (k(p-2))^2 - (m_1 - 1)(m_2 - 1) \\ q_1 &= (p-1)(p - (m_1 + 1))/q, & q_2 &= (p-1)(p - (m_2 + 1))/q. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 1. Let $k(p-2) + m_i - 1 > 0$, $i = 1, 2$, $\beta_1 \beta_2 > 1$ and

$$\frac{\beta_i + 1}{\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1 - (k(p-2) + m_i - 1)(\beta_i + 1)} < \frac{N}{p}, \quad i = 1, 2,$$

then

$$u_0(x) \leq u_+(0, x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad \nu_0(x) \leq \nu_+(0, x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^N.$$

then for solution of the Cauchy problem (1) the estimate

$$u(t, x) \leq u_+(t, x), \quad \nu(t, x) \leq \nu_+(t, x) \quad \text{in } Q.$$

hold.

We intend to show that the solution of problem (1) is globally solvable and possesses the property of finite speed of propagation (FSP).

Proof. The proof of the theorem is based on the comparison principle. As comparison functions, we take the following functions.

$$\begin{aligned} u_+(t, x) &= \bar{u}(t) \bar{f}(\xi), & \nu_+(t, x) &= \bar{v}(t) \bar{\psi}(\xi) \\ \bar{f}(\xi) &= (a - \xi^{p/(p-1)})_+^{q_1}, & \bar{\psi}(\xi) &= (a - \xi^{p/(p-1)})_+^{q_2} \end{aligned}$$

with property

$$u_+(t, x) \equiv 0, \quad \nu_+(t, x) \equiv 0 \quad \text{in } Q \setminus D$$

Functions $u_+(t, x)$, $\nu_+(t, x) \in C_{t,x}^{1,2} \cap C(\bar{D})$ in $D = \{(t, x) : t > 0, |x| < a^{\frac{(p-1)}{p}} [\tau(t)]^{1/p}\}$. Now we check condition $L_1(u_+, \nu_+) \leq 0$, $L_2(u_+, \nu_+) \leq 0$ in $D = \{(t, x) : t > 0, |x| < a^{(p-1)/p} [\tau(t)]^{1/p}\}$. Simple calculation shows that $L_1(u_+, \nu_+) \leq 0$, $L_2(u_+, \nu_+) \leq 0$.

Due to the comparison theorem [2] the proof is completed.

Remark. Notice that the Fujita type critical exponent for the system (1) is the following

$$\frac{\beta_i + 1}{\beta_1 \beta_2 - 1 - (k(p-2) + m_i - 1)(\beta_i + 1)} < \frac{N}{p}, \quad i = 1, 2.$$

This result consists of the result of Escobedo and Herrero [1] for the case when in (1) the parameter values are as follows: $p = 2$, $k(p-2) + m_i - 1 = 0$, $i = 1, 2$.

When $p = 2$, this theorem in the single-equation case was proved by H.Fujita [2]; for the p -Laplacian equation case ($m_i - 1 = 0$, $i = 1, 2$) it was obtained by V.Galaktionov [7].

The Fujita type global solution in the critical case

Theorem 2. Let $m_i + k(p - 2) - 1 = 0$, $i = 1, 2$, $(\beta_1 + 1)/(\beta_1\beta_2 - 1) > \frac{N}{p}$,
 $(\beta_2 + 1)/(\beta_1\beta_2 - 1) > \frac{N}{p}$, $u_0(x) \leq u_-(0, x)$, $\nu_0(x) \leq \nu_-(0, x)$, $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$.

Then for the solution of problem (1) the estimate

$$u(t, x) \leq u_-(t, x) = (T + t)^{-N/p} \exp(-(\xi/p)^p), \quad \xi = |x|/(T + t)^{1/p},$$

$$\nu(t, x) \leq \nu_-(t, x) = (T + t)^{-N/p} \exp(-(\xi/p)^p)$$

hold.

The proof of Theorem 2 is based on the comparison principle.

Notice that when $p = 2$ we have the Fujita type critical exponent [1], which was earlier proved by Escobedo and Herrero.

Remark. Notice that in the case $p = 2$, $\beta_1 = \beta_2$, $m_i = 1$, $i = 1, 2$, the condition (1) turns to the global solvability Fujita result for the one-equation case [2]: $\beta > 1 + 2/N$.

2. Asymptotic of self-similar solutions

Below we list a theorem concerning the asymptotic behaviour of self-similar solutions in the slowly and fast diffusion cases.

Theorem 3. Assume $(q_1/q) > 0$, $(q_2/q) > 0$. Then the weak compactly supported solutions $f(\xi)$, $\psi(\xi)$ of the system (1) as $\eta \rightarrow \infty$, where $\eta = -\ln(a - \xi^{p/(p-1)})$, have asymptotic

$$f(\xi) = c_1 \bar{f}(\xi)(1 + o(1)), \quad \psi(\xi) = c_2 \bar{\psi}(\xi)(1 + o(1)),$$

where the coefficients c_1, c_2 satisfy the system of algebraic equations

$$-(q_1) c_1^{p-1} c_1^{m_1+k(p-2)-1} + a_1 \gamma^{-p} = 0,$$

$$-(q_2) c_2^{p-1} c_2^{m_2+k(p-2)-1} + a_2 \gamma^{-p} = 0.$$

3. Fast diffusion case

Theorem 4. Let $m_i + k(p - 2) - 1 < 0$, $i = 1, 2$. Then the quenching solution of the system (1) as $\eta \rightarrow \infty$ where $\eta = -\ln(a - \xi^{p/(p-1)})$ has the asymptotic form

$$f(\xi) = c_3 \left(a + \xi^{p/(p-1)} \right)^{q_1}, \quad \psi(\xi) = c_4 \left(a + \xi^{p/(p-1)} \right)^{q_2}.$$

The coefficients c_3, c_4 are the roots of the nonlinear system of algebraic equations

$$\gamma^{p-1}(N + \gamma q_1)c_3^{m_1+k(p-2)} + \left(a_1q_1 + \frac{\beta_1 + 1}{\beta_1\beta_2 - 1}\right)c_3 + c_4^{\beta_1} = 0,$$

$$\gamma^{p-1}(N + \gamma q_2)c_4^{m_2+k(p-2)} + \left(a_2q_2 + \frac{\beta_2 + 1}{\beta_1\beta_2 - 1}\right)c_4 + c_3^{\beta_2} = 0.$$

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